

Class Size, Availability and Use of Instructional Resources as Correlates of Academic Performance of Primary Two Pupils in Ido Local Government Area

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and

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Abstract

The quality of primary education a child receives determines the success of the child at other levels of education because primary education is the bedrock of other levels of education in every country. Class size and instructional resources for teaching are some of the important indicators of effective teaching and learning in primary schools. This study therefore investigated class size, availability and use of instructional resources as correlates of academic performance of primary two pupils in Ido Local Government Area of Oyo State. Correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. The study involved 30 public primary schools randomly selected from Ido Local Government Area as well as 30 primary two teachers and 832 pupils of 30 primary two intact classes. Two instruments were used for data Collection, Checklist on Availability and Use of Instructional Resources in Public Primary Schools (CAUIRPPS) and Class Size and Primary Two Pupils Performance in Core Subjects (CSPTPPCS). The instrument were presented to some primary two teachers to know if the items listed in the instrument are appropriate for teaching primary two pupils after which necessary adjustment was made on face, content and construct validity and items found unsuitable were removed. 20 copies was produced and administered to primary II teachers of public primary schools to check the reliability of the instrument. The reliability was tested using Cronbach Alpha and the coefficient obtained was 0.76. Three research questions were answered and four hypotheses were tested using descriptive statistics (frequency count, simple percentage and mean) and inferential statistics of multiple regression and correlation respectively. The findings showed that the average class size of primary two pupils in Ido Local Government Area is 28. Availability and use of instructional resources is below average. There is a significant negative relationship between class size and academic performance of primary two pupils ($r = -0.44$; $P < 0.05$). Also, there is no significant relationship between the use of instructional resources and academic performance of primary two pupils ($r = 0.43$; $P > 0.05$). Based on the findings of the research, it was recommended that government should maintain the present average class size which is within the range of what National Policy on Education recommended.

Key words: Class Size, Availability, Utilization, Performance, primary school pupils.

Introduction

In every society, the quality of primary education received by a child determines the achievement of the child in all other levels of education; this is because primary education is the bedrock of other levels of education (Akande, 2017). It is very important for every child to acquire primary education because it inculcates so many good values, habits and morals that the society uphold and this is why it is made compulsory by government in every country. An individual might not have the opportunity to complete other levels of education but primary education is compulsory for every citizen since it is the most accessible level of education in many countries.

Primary education is an important level of education which gives an individual great opportunity to be able to contribute in transforming the society. Primary education is available in both developed and developing countries of the world as well as in rural and urban areas of every state. Enrolment is easy and accessible to all school aged children irrespective of gender, geographical, social, cultural and economic background (Akinbote, 2016). This is because primary education is an education that exposes the young ones to the basic things they need to know about their society and the basic knowledge they need to acquire for them to be able to function effectively in the society. Etor, Mbon and Ekanem (2013), describes primary education as the key to a child's development in every society because whatever a child learn in primary school will stay with him/her throughout his/her life. This explains why primary education is seen as the foundation of all other levels of education in all countries. Okwori and Henry (2014), assert that primary education is the education that is given after nursery education to children. All other systems of education is built upon primary education and this makes it to be the key to the success or failure of educational system of any country.

Primary education is a must for everybody, as it is the level of education which develops in the individual the ability to learn, to read, to acquire information, to write and to calculate in such a way that it eradicates illiteracy (Akinbote, 2016). This implies that primary education was designed to develop children in all forms and to prepare them for all other levels of education. National Policy on Education defines primary education as the education that is given to children aged of 6-12 years (FRN, 2013). It is tailored towards inculcating permanent literacy, numeracy and the ability to communicate effectively. It helps children learn how to adapt to environmental changes and also creates opportunities for children to develop life manipulative skills which will make them to function effectively in the society based on their capabilities. Primary education lays a sound basis for critical, scientific and reflective thinking and also instils social, moral norms and values in children (FRN, 2013).

Without learning education cannot take place, learning occurs as a result of newly acquired information, facts, knowledge, principles, and skills (Ogaga, Igori and Egbodo, 2016). Learning is also a relatively permanent change in human behaviour due to his or her prior acquired experience that involves observable activities as well as internal processes such as emotions, attitude, thinking and belief. It is a process that starts from when a child is born and go with him or her till the child dies. The major reason for enrolling children in primary school is to acquire good moral and positive behaviour under the supervision of adults (Alao and Adeniyi, 2008). Primary school systems have now established a primary means of learning which involves groups of pupils of the same age interacting with one or more experienced adults leading activities in a restricted physical space, directed toward facilitating learning a particular topic. This means that pupils are placed in various classes which may be large or small.

Class size is the total number of pupils who are always present in the classroom with a teacher during instruction and for whom that teacher is responsible, (Jeremy, Susan and Jayne, 2005). The exact class size varies from school to school, this means that the number of pupils in a class in one school will not be the same with the number of pupils in a class in another school, Bascia (2010) asserts that when class size is under teachers control, it will enable such teacher to pay attention to pupils individuality in the classroom, assess them frequently, engage them in practical activities with close monitoring and also respond to pupils individual needs. Class size might be an obvious and easily available measure of pupils' academic performance, but the number of pupils in a class at a particular time might be different to the number of pupils in a class based on the class register. This is because some of these pupils may be absent from school at the time of instruction. In this case, the class size of a school is the total number of pupils present in a classroom for instruction. Class size therefore refers to the exact number of pupils taught by a teacher at a particular time of instruction. That is, it is the total number of pupils who are physically present in the classroom, interacting among themselves and with the teacher (Ronald, Dominic, Adam and Douglas, 2001). Knowing each pupil personally might be difficult for teachers in large class and to also tailor instruction that will cater for individual needs of pupils might be difficult (Ngoboka and Schultz, 2002).

Joseph and Philius (2011) noted that class size is the decision of school management or school owners over which teachers have little or no control. Many researchers are of the opinion that the size of a class would have influence on the degree of success of pupils. With the increase in class size the academic performance of pupils needs to be checked. The National Policy on Education states that "for effective teaching and learning, the teacher-pupil ratio shall be 1:35 for primary level" (FRN, 2013). This shows that Government is aware of the fact that class size is an important factor in the academic performance of primary school pupils. Schanzenbach (2014) and Mathis (2016) noted that class size is very important and necessary in determining pupils' outcomes, starting from their test scores to broader life outcome. He further explained that smaller classes are more effective and good at raising pupils' performance levels and that increasing class size will harm pupils' performance. When class size is increasing simply because school owners do not want to incur additional cost by employing more teachers and putting in more resources, it will surely tell on the children's academic performance tomorrow.

Abdul-Raheem (2016), attested that instructional resources are needed for effective teaching and learning. Learning can be reinforced with various instructional resources to arouse pupils' interest to instruction. Ogaga, Igori and Egbodo (2016), describes instructional resources as learning materials that are used for instruction in the classroom or at workshops for better understanding of concepts. According to Okune, Gudo, and Odongo (2016), instructional resources are materials used by teachers in the process of teaching and learning to make the content of what they are delivering more interesting, vivid and pragmatic to learners. Instructional resources vary from simple and inexpensive ones, such as text books, flash cards, flat pictures, counters, diagrams, work sheets, chalkboard, and maps, to more complex and expensive ones like computers, movie projectors, television, slides and filmstrip projectors. Instructional resources are grouped into two which are; printed and non-printed materials. Instructional resources could also be classified into; audio-aids, visual-aids and audio-visual. Audio-aids are resources which appeal to sense of hearing alone such as radio and tape recorder, visual-aids are resources which appeal to sense of sight alone such as charts, pictures, objects and so on, while audio-visual are resources which appeal to both the sense of sight and hearing.

The quality of teaching and its effectiveness depends mainly on the availability of good and appropriate instructional resources. However, despite the numerous advantages inherent in the use of instructional resources in the process of teaching and learning, it is embarrassing to note that many teachers and schools in Nigeria still base their teaching on textbook and chalkboards, with the teachers being the alpha and omega of the teaching and learning process. Majority of them neglect the importance of using instructional resources as a tool in enhancing the academic performance of the pupils in primary schools (Ogunwale, 2015). It is important for instructional resources to be available in schools in order to achieve effectiveness in instructional delivery. Dada and Babalola (2014), assert that for effective teaching and learning of all subjects, instructional resources have to be employed in their different forms. Schools must be equipped with different types of relevant instructional resources and make them available for use. This is because the usage of instructional resources facilitates effective teaching and learning.

The effective utilization of instructional resources is important in helping pupils to quickly assimilate what is being taught in the classroom. Teachers, pupils, chalk or marker, board and textbooks are seen as conventional resources used in instructional delivery process. All these instructional resources are not enough to facilitate effective teaching and learning in the classroom. If instructional resources are available, inappropriate usage of the resources amount to non-availability of instructional resources. Effiong and Igiri (2015) reported that the use of instructional resources enhances learning achievement and make pupils have interest in the teaching and learning process. When instructional resources are used in teaching and learning, it will help learners to have positive attitude towards learning, it will make them understand better what is being taught easily, it will develop problem solving skills in them, and also develop their manipulative skills Ogunwale (2015). Understanding what is being taught easily depends on how the teacher can carry the pupils in the class along and this will later determine pupils' academic performance.

Academic performance is defined in terms of examination performance which is characterized by performance in tests, in course work and performance in examinations (Kyoshaba, 2009). It is the measurable behaviour of pupils in an examination which consists of scores obtained from teacher-made test, mid-semester test, end of term examinations, public examinations and so on. Jayanthi et al (2014) define academic performance in terms of performance in examination which is based on the overall performance of pupils at the end of the term or session.

There are many factors contributing to the poor academic performance of primary school pupils. They include; the physical setting of a school, lack of a conducive learning environment, quality of teachers and learning resources. Ntibi and Edoho (2017), lamented that the poor performance of pupils in public examinations such as common entrance examination may also be due to lack of understanding of simple concept and processes. This could happen due to pupils' failure to pay attention to the learning of concepts, techniques and processes when they were being taught in the classroom. Some studies such as Shittu and Oanite (2015), examined how teachers attitude influence teaching and learning of primary school pupils in social studies while Omiko (2016) investigated some factors that could affect academic performance of pupils which includes; lack of trained teachers, lack of proper teaching materials, absence of conducive teaching and learning environment, inadequate evaluation or probably, inadequate teaching methods. Other studies such as Peter, Paul and Penelope (2011), investigated effect of class size on two key processes: pupil classroom engagement and teacher-pupil interactions while Ogunwale (2015), examined the effect of availability and utilization of instructional materials on public primary school pupils performance. However, there is need to further investigate the effect of class size, availability

and use of instructional resources on the academic performance of primary two pupils in the core subjects.

Academic performance of primary school pupils is one of the important indications of effective teaching and learning in schools in almost every country of the world. Available research reports show that the poor performance of primary school pupils in school tests and examinations is becoming a source of concern to parents and teachers as well as the general public. This has been attributed among other things to the non-availability of instructional resources or inappropriate utilization of instructional resources. Efforts to address this issue of poor performance have led various scholars into researching how the improvement of teachers' motivation, teachers' qualification, supervision, provision and adequate use of instructional resources and class size can bring some improvement to pupils' academic performance.

However, bringing class size, availability and use of instructional resources together in a single study as correlates of academic performance of primary school pupils for optimum academic performance has neither been fully captured nor given much attention by previous studies. Therefore, this study investigated class size, availability and use of instructional resources as correlates of academic performance of primary two pupils in Ido Local Government Area of Oyo State.

Theoretical Framework

Social Constructivist Theory (Lev Vygotsky)

This theory states that social interaction comes before development; consciousness and cognition are the end product of socialization and social behaviour. What is important in this theory is teacher's intervention in children's learning, because the quality of teacher-learner interaction is very crucial to learning. This theory is relevant to this work because it emphasises interaction between teacher and small group of pupils. This means that when pupils are too many in a classroom there would not be effective interaction. Social constructivist theory emphasizes that learners should construct their knowledge based on interaction with their teachers or other knowledgeable individuals, their peers and the environment and this can be achieved depending on the class size or the number of learners involved (Akintemi, 2018).

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to be an eye-opener to teachers in the primary schools, parents, school owners, government and the general public on how class size, availability and use of instructional resources will enhance academic performance of primary school pupils which will in turn make teaching and learning more interesting to the pupils. It also envisages that the result of the study will show how attention span of pupils would increase and how they would be able to remember whatever they were taught after the introduction of instructional resources.

Research Questions

The following three research questions were raised in this study.

1. What is the average class size of primary two classes of public primary schools in Ido Local Government Area of Oyo State?

2. What is the level of availability of instructional resources in primary two classes of public primary schools in Ido Local Government Area?
3. What is the level of utilization of instructional resources in primary two classes in Ido Local Government Area?

Hypotheses

The following four hypotheses were tested in this study.

- 1 Ho₁: There is no significant composite contribution of class size, availability and utilization of instructional resources on primary two pupils academic performance.
- 2 Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between class size and academic performance of primary two pupils.
- 3 Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between availability of instructional resources and academic performance of primary two pupils.
- 4 Ho₄: There is no significant relationship between the use of instructional resources and academic performance of primary two pupils.

Methodology

The correlational survey research design was adopted for this study. The population involved all primary two teachers and pupils in Ido Local Government Area of Oyo State. Random sampling technique was used to select 30 schools in Ido Local Government Area. However, 30 teachers of primary two classes were involved in this study. The reason for the selection of primary two teachers was that the study focused on primary two pupils and automatically primary two teachers are the ones to provide the information needed in carrying out this study. Primary two pupils were chosen because at this level they need more instructional resources for them to understand whatever they are taught better than pupils in the upper classes. One intact primary two class from each school with a total of 832 pupils in all were involved in the study.

Two research instruments were used, the first one was: A Checklist on Availability and Use of Instructional Resources in Public Primary Schools (CAUIRPPS, $\alpha=0.76$) adapted from Ajala (2017) was designed to measure the “availability and adequacy of school facilities and learning resources in Primary Schools”. The second one is a self-designed instrument to take class inventory, class size and primary two pupils’ performance in core subjects. Pupils’ individual performance was retrieved from their teachers’ record in second term examinations as that was the last examinations they wrote before the study was conducted.

60 questionnaires (30 for the first instrument and 30 for the second instrument) were administered to the teachers and all were duly completed by the researcher. The administration of the instrument took three weeks. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics which includes; frequency count, percentage, mean, standard deviation; and inferential statistics of multiple regression and correlation.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the average class size of primary II classes of public primary schools in Ido Local Government Area of Oyo State?

Table 1: Average Class Size of Primary II Pupils.

Class Size	Frequency	Percent	Average Class Size	Std. Deviation
5.00	1	3.3		
7.00	1	3.3		
12.00	2	6.7		
15.00	2	6.7		
20.00	2	6.7		
21.00	1	3.3		
22.00	1	3.3		
23.00	4	13.3		
24.00	1	3.3		
25.00	1	3.3	27.733	13.29
26.00	1	3.3		
30.00	2	6.7		
32.00	2	6.7		
33.00	1	3.3		
35.00	1	3.3		
38.00	1	3.3		
39.00	1	3.3		
43.00	2	6.7		
46.00	1	3.3		
50.00	1	3.3		
65.00	1	3.3		
Total	30	100.0		

Table 1 shows that the average class size of primary II classes of public primary schools in Ido Local Government Area of Oyo State is 27.73 pupils which can be approximated to 28 pupils.

Research Question 2: To what extent are instructional resources available in primary II classes of public primary schools in Ido Local Government Area?

Table 2: Availability of Instructional Resources in Primary II Classes.

S/N	ITEMS	AVAILABLE	NOT AVAILABLE
1.	English Language textbook for the teacher	26 (86.7%)	4 (13.3%)
2.	English Language textbook for the pupils	6 (20%)	24 (80%)
3.	English Language workbook for the teacher	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
4.	English Language workbook for the pupils	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
5.	Dictionary	18 (60%)	12 (40%)
6.	Tape Recorder	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
7.	Charts	15 (50%)	15 (50%)
8.	Mathematics textbook for the teacher	29 (96.7%)	1 (3.3%)
9.	Mathematics textbook for the pupils	7 (23.3%)	23 (76.7%)
10.	Mathematics workbook for the teacher	0 (0%)	100 (100%)

11.	Mathematics workbook for the pupils	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
12.	Measuring instruments such as: tape rule, scales, ruler, cup, spoon	28 (93.3%)	2 (6.7%)
13.	Mathematical charts	16 (53.3%)	14 (46.7%)
14.	Shapes of different colours	26 (86.7%)	4 (13.3%)
15.	Cardboard model	19 (63.3)	11 (36.7%)
16.	Basic science and Technology textbook for the teacher	100 (100%)	0 (0%)
17.	Basic science and Technology textbook for the pupils	6 (20%)	24 (80%)
18.	Basic science and Technology workbook for the pupils	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
19.	Science laboratory	2 (6.7%)	28 (93.3%)
20.	Basic science and technology charts	17 (56.7%)	13 (43.3%)
21.	Thermometer	5 (16.7%)	25 (83.3%)
22.	Computer	1 (3.3%)	29 (96.7%)
23.	Social studies textbook for the teachers	29 (96.7%)	1 (3.3%)
24.	Social studies textbook for the pupils	7 (23.3%)	23 (76.7%)
25.	Social studies Charts	12 (40%)	18 (60%)
26.	Maps	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
27.	Pictures	24 (80%)	6 (20%)
28.	Historical newspapers	3 (10%)	27 (90%)

Table 2 reveals that higher percentage (86.7%) of primary II teachers have English language textbook while only 6% of the pupils has English language textbook, none of the teachers and pupils have English language workbook, 60% of the teachers have dictionary, 50% of the schools has English language chart that relate to pronunciation while none of them have tape recorder. Higher percentage of teachers (96.7%) have mathematics textbook while just 7% of the pupils have mathematics textbook, none of the teachers and pupils have mathematics workbook, 93.3% has measuring instruments such as; ruler, tape rule, spoon and cup, 53.3% have mathematical chart, 86.7% have shapes of different colours, 63.3% have cardboard model. All the teachers (100%) have Basic Science and technology textbook while just 6% of the pupils have basic science and technology textbook, none of the pupils have Basic science and Technology workbook, 6.7% of the schools have science laboratory, 5% have thermometer, 3.3% have computer, 56.7% have Basic science and Technology chart. Also, 96.7% have social studies textbook while just 7% of the pupils have social studies textbook, only 12% of the schools have chart that relate to social studies, none of the schools have map, 80% of the teachers have pictures to show for their teaching while just 3% has historical newspapers.

Give a brief explanation of how you come about table 3 and which research question it is addressing.

Table 3: Availability of Instructional Resources Based on Schools.**AVAILABILITY OF RESOURCES BASED ON SCHOOLS**

Number of Available Resources	Frequency(schools)	Percent
7.00	1	3.3
8.00	4	13.3
9.00	7	23.3
10.00	3	10.0
11.00	4	13.3
12.00	3	10.0
13.00	3	10.0
14.00	2	6.7
15.00	1	3.3
16.00	2	6.7
Total	30	100.0

Table 3 reveals that only 5 schools out of 30 schools have instructional resources that are average and above the remaining 25 schools are below average. Out of all the 28 instructional resources checked; 2 schools have 14 which is average, 1 school have 15 which is above average and 2 schools have 16 which is also above average. This shows that the level of availability of instructional resources in schools is very low and not encouraging.

Research Question 3: To what extent do primary II teachers in Ido Local Government Area make use of instructional resources?

Table 4: Extent at Which Instructional Resources Are Being Used in Primary II Classes.

S/N	ITEMS	USE	NOT USE
1.	English Language textbook for the teacher	28 (93.3%)	2 (6.7%)
2.	English Language textbook for the pupils	6 (20%)	24 (80%)
3.	English Language workbook for the teacher	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
4.	English Language workbook for the pupils	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
5.	Dictionary	18 (60%)	12 (40%)
6.	Tape Recorder	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
7.	Charts	15 (50%)	15 (50%)
8.	Mathematics textbook for the teacher	29 (96.7%)	1 (3.3%)
9.	Mathematics textbook for the pupils	7 (23.3%)	23 (76.7%)
10.	Mathematics workbook for the teacher	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
11.	Mathematics workbook for the pupils	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
12.	Measuring instruments such as: tape rule, scales, ruler, cup, spoon	28 (93.3%)	2 (6.7%)
13.	Mathematical charts	15 (50%)	15 (50%)

14.	Shapes of different colours	27 (90%)	3 (10%)
15.	Cardboard model	20 (66.7%)	10 (33.3%)
16.	Basic science and Technology textbook for the teacher	100 (100%)	0 (0%)
17.	Basic science and Technology textbook for the pupils	4 (13.3%)	26 (86.7%)
18.	Basic science and Technology workbook for the pupils	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
19.	Science laboratory	1 (3.3%)	29 (96.7%)
20.	Basic science and technology charts	17 (56.7%)	13 (43.3%)
21.	Thermometer	4 (13.3%)	26 (86.7%)
22.	Computer	2 (6.7%)	28 (93.3%)
23.	Social studies textbook for the teachers	29 (96.7%)	1 (3.3%)
24.	Social studies textbook for the pupils	4 (13.3%)	26 (86.7%)
25.	Social studies Charts	11 (36.7%)	19 (63.3%)
26.	Maps	0 (0%)	100 (100%)
27.	Pictures	24 (80%)	6 (20%)
28.	Historical newspapers	3 (10%)	27 (90%)

Table 4 shows that higher percentage (93.3%) of primary II teachers are making use of English language textbook while only 20% of the pupils are using it, both the teachers and pupils are not making use of English language workbook, 60% are using dictionary for better performance of their pupils, none of the teachers is using tape recorder and chart to teach English language, 96.7% of the teachers and 23.3% of pupils are making use of mathematics textbook while both the teachers and pupils are not using mathematics workbook, 93.3% are using measuring instruments such as; ruler, tape rule, spoon and cup in their teaching, only 50% are using mathematical chart, 90% are using shapes of different colours to teach their pupils, 66.7% are making use of cardboard model, all the teachers (100%) are making use of Basic Science and technology textbook but 13.3% of the pupils are using basic science textbook while none of the pupils has basic science and technology workbook. 3.3% of the teachers is making use of science laboratory to teach, 56.7% of the teachers are making use of Basic science and Technology chart, 13.3% are using thermometer, 6.7% are making use of computer, 96.7% of the teachers are using social studies textbook while just 13.3% of the pupils are using social studies textbook, 36.7% of the teachers are making use of chart when teaching social studies while none of the teachers are using map to teach, 80% of them are making use of pictures during teaching. Also, only 10% are making use of historical newspaper.

Table 5: Utilization of Instructional Resources Based on Schools.

Number of Resources	Frequency(schools)	Percent
7.00	3	10.0
8.00	4	13.3
9.00	3	10.0
10.00	5	16.7
11.00	5	16.7
12.00	2	6.7
13.00	3	10.0
14.00	3	10.0
16.00	1	3.3
17.00	1	3.3
Total	30	100.0

Table 5 shows that out of all the 28 instructional resources, 3 teachers are using 14 instructional resources which is on the average, 1 teacher is using 16 instructional resources which is above average and 17 instructional resources are being used by 1 teacher. This shows that the level of instructional resources utilization is also very low and not encouraging.

Research Hypothesis Ho₁: There is no significant composite contribution of independent variables on dependent variable?

Table 7: Summary of Multiple Regressions on Class Size, Availability and Utilization of Instructional Resources on Pupils Performance.

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F	Sig.
Regression	416.522	3	138.841	2.756	.063
Residual	1309.899	26	50.381		
Total	1726.421	29			
R	.491				
R ²	.241				
Adjusted R ²	.154				

Table 7 shows that the three independent variables have relationship with the dependent variable ($R=0.49$). This leads to the fact that the three independent variables accounted for 15.4% of the total variance in the dependent variable. This composite contribution is shown not to be significant ($F_{(3,26)} = 2.76$; $P > 0.05$). Therefore, class size, availability and use of instructional resources have no significant composite contribution on pupils' academic performance.

Research Hypothesis Ho₂: There is a significant relationship between class size and academic performance of primary II pupils.

Table 8: Relationship between Class Size, Availability and Use of Instructional Resources and Academic Performance of Primary II Pupils.**Correlations**

Variables	N	Class Size	Availability	Utilization	Performance
Class Size	30	1	-.042	.000	-.435*
Availability	30	-.042	1	.900**	.228
Utilization	30	.000	.900**	1	.151
Performance	30	-.435*	.228	.151	1

Table 8 shows that there is a –ve (negative) significant relationship between class size and academic performance of primary II pupils ($r = -0.44$; $P < 0.05$). Therefore, **H₀₁** is rejected.

Research Hypothesis **H₀₃**: There is no significant relationship between availability of instructional resources and academic performance of primary II pupils.

Table 8 reveals that there is no significant relationship between availability of instructional resources and academic performance of primary II pupils ($r = 0.23$; $P > 0.05$). Hence, **H₀₂** is not rejected.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between the use of instructional resources and academic performance of primary II pupils.

Table 8 reveals that there is no significant relationship between the use of instructional resources and academic performance of primary II pupils ($r = 0.15$; $P > 0.05$). Therefore, **H₀₃** is not rejected. Table 8 also reveals that there is a significant positive relationship between availability and utilization of instructional resources ($r = 0.90$; $P < 0.05$).

Discussions of Findings

According to this research, the average class size of primary II pupils in Ido Local Government Area of Oyo State is 28. Findings from this study revealed that only 5 primary II classes out of 30 visited have instructional resources that are average and above while 25 primary II classes have resources that are below average. Textbooks are the most available resources in primary two classes as textbooks carries higher percentage of available instructional resources, this supports the findings of Omuna, Onchera, and Kimutai (2016) that textbooks are the most available instructional resources in schools. With this, the availability of instructional resources in primary 2 classes is below average.

It was also revealed from this study that only 5 teachers are making use of instructional resources on the average and above, with this the utilization of instructional resources in primary 2 classes is below average. This supports the findings of Ogunwale (2015) that the level of utilization of instructional materials in schools are not encouraging and highly of low usage.

This study revealed that there is a significant –ve (negative) relationship between class size and academic performance of primary II pupils. This negative relationship means that when class size is increasing academic performance of primary two pupils is decreasing. This result corroborates with the findings of Fidler (2001), Bakasa (2011), and Marais (2016), they found that there is a relationship between class size and pupils academic performance. It is also in consonance with Zyngier (2014) assertion that class size is a great determinant of pupils academic outcomes. The result of this study negates the findings of Ngoboka and Schultz (2002), Owoeye and Yara (2011), that class size has nothing to do with pupils academic performance.

The findings from the study showed no significant relationship between availability of instructional resources and academic performance of primary two pupils. Also, the result showed no significant relationship between the use of instructional resources and academic performance of primary two pupils. This finding support the result of the studies conducted by Iheonunekwu and Ndidi (2014) which showed that there is no significant relationship between utilization of resources and students' academic performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that the average class size of primary two pupils is within the range of recommended National Policy on Education teacher-pupils ratio which should be maintained because class size plays a significant role in the academic performance of primary two pupils. This study also concluded that availability and utilization of instructional resources does not affect academic performance of primary two pupils, it depends on the effectiveness of the teacher, how the teacher can explain concepts and carry the pupils along during instruction.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations are made.

1. Government should maintain the present teacher-pupils ratio(1:35) recommended by the National Policy on Education to improve pupils performance.
2. Enough instructional resources should be made available for teachers and pupils to access directly.
3. Government should provide resource centres where teachers can borrow materials that are not available in schools.
4. Teachers should be encouraged to attend conferences, seminars and workshops to update their knowledge on how to improvise instructional materials.
5. Teachers should also learn how to improvise simple instructional materials needed for their teaching.

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